

Persistent Identifiers: A Prerequisite to Establish the Framework for Scholarly Link Exchange-Scholix

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The Scholix framework—Scholarly Link Exchange—is a set of aspirational principles and practical guidelines developed under the umbrella of a joint Working Group of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the World Data System (WDS). It supports a global open information ecosystem unveiling the links between scholarly literature and underpinning research data.

The core objectives of the framework are to (1) increase visibility and discoverability of data and articles, (2) place data in context to enable re-use, and (3) support credit attribution mechanisms. Thus, facilitating reproducibility and the transparent evaluation of science.

Scholix provides an evolving lightweight set of Guidelines to increase interoperability rather than a normative standard. It consists initially of a conceptual and information models, information standards and encoding guidelines, and options for encoding and exchange protocols.

An essential prerequisite to enable the proposed framework is the use of global, unique and persistent identifiers for research objects (such as data and literature). Scholix provides incentives and encourages best practice in the use of such identifiers and standardised referencing.

The Data and Literature Interlinking Service (DLI: <http://dliservice.research-infrastructures.eu/>) is the first exemplar of an aggregation and query service supported by the Scholix framework which will allow the emergence of third party services such as domain-specific aggregations, integrations with other global services, discovery tools, impact assessments, etc.

Scholix is already implemented by existing hubs or global aggregators of data-literature link information such as DataCite, CrossRef, OpenAIRE, and EMBL-EBI building on the capacities of existing Persistent Identifier Systems (PIDs) such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) and Accession Numbers. These hubs in turn work with their natural communities of data centres or literature publishers to collect the information through existing community-specific workflows and standards.

Scholix as a technical solution to wholesale information aggregation will need to be complemented by other policy, practice and cultural change advocacy initiatives. This approach could be extended over time to other types of research objects in and beyond research.